

Dynamic Façade Design based on Visual Comfort and Daylight Performance Optimization

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ABSTRACT

The building envelope plays an important role in the control of the natural daylight demand at a building scale. An optimized configuration of the façade can contribute to reduce in the total energy consumption of the building. Recently, there has been an increase in the work on responsive building facades, which can offer to increase indoor visual comfort while reducing energy consumption. In order to provide this, kinetic structures with foldable elements can be used to provide variation in the building envelope by motion.

In contrast to rigid shading elements, dynamic façade elements having different configurations can provide an effective solution for controlling solar radiation and daylight. The aim of this paper is to evaluate the main parameters determining the geometry and the kinematic behavior of dynamic shading elements based on loop-based method [1], and their effect on the performance as a shading system.

In this study, a shading module has been constructed by the loop-based method. The parametric model of the system has been modelled in Grasshopper® to evaluate the geometry of the building while providing the visual comfort of the interior. The parametric model generates the case building and the shading elements in a virtual environment. Two plug-ins for Grasshopper® (Ladybug and Honeybee) have been used to calculate the daylight performance. Since shading elements cover most of the facades, visual perception of the user in the interior space have been also calculated, as a counter objective. To simulate the visual comfort provided by each shading alternative, a geometry-based calculation method has been used within the software. Later, as a multi-objective evolutionary optimization tool, Octopus has been used to search for many goals at once and to produce optimized solutions for each goals to be satisfied by using Pareto-principle.

References

- [1] F. Maden, Y. Akgün, G. Kiper, Ş. Gür, M. Yar, & K. Korkmaz, A Critical Review on Classification and Terminology of Scissor Structures. *Journal of the International Association for Shell and Spatial Structures*, **60**(1), 47-64, 2019.